

Educational Artificial Intelligent Chatbot: Teacher Assistant & Study Buddy

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Master Programme in Data Science
2023

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Date: 2023-07-26

Abstract

In the rapidly evolving landscape of artificial intelligence, the potential of large language models (LLMs) remains a focal point of exploration, especially in the domain of education. This research delves into the capabilities of AI-enhanced chatbots, with a spotlight on the "Teacher Assistant" & "Study Buddy" approaches. The study highlights the role of AI in offering adaptive learning experiences and personalized recommendations. As educational institutions and platforms increasingly turn to AI-driven solutions, understanding the intricacies of how LLMs can be harnessed to create meaningful and accurate educational content becomes paramount.

The research adopts a systematic and multi-faceted methodology. At its core, the study investigates the interplay between prompt construction, engineering techniques, and the resulting outputs of the LLM. Two primary methodologies are employed: the application of prompt structuring techniques and the introduction of advanced prompt engineering methods. The former involves a progressive application of techniques like persona and template, aiming to discern their individual and collective impacts on the LLM's outputs. The latter delves into more advanced techniques, such as the few-shot prompt and chain-of-thought prompt, to gauge their influence on the quality and characteristics of the LLM's responses. Complementing these is the "Study Buddy" approach, where curricula from domains like biology, mathematics, and physics are utilized as foundational materials for the experiments.

The findings from this research are poised to have significant implications for the future of AI in education. By offering a comprehensive understanding of the variables that influence an LLM's performance, the study paves the way for the development of more refined and effective AI-driven educational tools. As educators and institutions grapple with the challenges of modern education, tools that can generate accurate, relevant, and diverse educational content can be invaluable. This thesis not only contributes to the academic understanding of LLMs and provides practical insights that can shape the future of AI-enhanced education, but as education continues to evolve, the findings underscore the need for ongoing exploration and refinement to fully leverage AI's benefits in the educational sector.

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1. Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is the ability of machines to perform complex tasks typically requiring human intelligence. These tasks can include problem-solving, planning, understanding natural language, recognizing patterns, learning, and the list keeps growing.

The rapid evolution of Artificial Intelligence research continually presents new solutions to complex problems and significant improvements to the quality of human life. One noteworthy example is the study conducted by Mokayed et al., (2023), where the performance of vehicle detectors under varied snowy weather conditions was analyzed using data captured by Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs). The research provides a comprehensive account of data preparation procedures and introduces a multi-feature deconvolutional Faster R-CNN model for accurate vehicle detection in aerial imagery, utilizing the Nordic Vehicle Dataset (NVD) for experimental validation. However, advancements in the field of medical imaging are presented in the work by Voon et al., (2022), where they assessed the effectiveness of seven distinct Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) in grading Invasive Ductal Carcinoma (IDC) in breast histopathological images using transfer learning. This research not only highlights the practical application of CNNs for IDC grade classification but also presents a comparative performance analysis of the seven CNN models against the image distribution data from BreakHis and the BCG dataset. Lastly, addressing the challenge of scarce data in document image classification, Kanchi et al., (2022) propose an efficient multimodal method that combines textual streams with dynamic word embedding and hierarchical attention networks. Their innovative approach, encompassing techniques such as adaptive thresholding and multimodal side-tuning, yields higher overall accuracy compared to earlier models. This confluence of research illustrates the broad impact and potential of AI across varied domains and conditions. Also, AI can be used in different applications like Security and surveillance (Mokayed et al., 2022), intelligent transportation system (Khan et al., 2022), and numerous other fields. This study specifically concentrates on the use of AI on the education. Education is the most crucial element in fostering a prosperous society. A thriving community depends on a solid educational foundation to promote the growth and well-being of its members. The development of education has been characterized by ongoing advancements and breakthroughs, leading to a wealth of knowledge and possibilities for all. Moving forward, it is essential to prioritize the creation of well-rounded educational programs, build inclusive learning spaces, and encourage critical thinking. By laying a strong educational groundwork, we enable individuals to make meaningful contributions to society, nurture a sense of global responsibility, and pave the way for enduring progress for everyone.

The time is ripe for AI to make its way into schools and begin delivering significant benefits. One such example is IBM Watson, a supercomputer-powered AI, serving as an administrative assistant to students at Deakin University. This innovative use of AI exemplifies the potential of integrating advanced technology in academia, offering a dynamic, interactive learning experience while streamlining administrative tasks (Boateng et al., 2022). Watson can provide service to the students at any time. This results in a different structure within the administrative power of the university with fewer personnel. Now the students get an immediate answer depending on their profile.

In recent years, the educational systems have integrated computers and other forms of technology in their teaching methodologies. This transition has led to the widespread use of devices such as tablets and laptops in classrooms, enhancing the learning experience for students. Teachers are now incorporating various digital tools and platforms to facilitate collaborative learning. The implementation of technologies like interactive whiteboards, learning management systems, and online resources has not only made lessons more engaging but also expanded the boundaries of the traditional classrooms, connecting students and

educators across the globe. As a result, students are acquiring valuable digital skills that prepare them for success in an increasingly technology-driven world.

1.1 Current problems in Education

Despite the integration of computerized technology into the educational systems, there remain several challenges to be addressed in order to truly revolutionize education. Some of these issues include:

1. **Uniformity in education:** Current educational systems often follow a one-size-fits-all approach, failing to cater to the individual strengths and weaknesses of each student. This can hinder students from realizing their full potential and receiving the targeted support they need to excel.
2. **Slow feedback:** Teachers may sometimes provide feedback slowly, resulting in delayed notifications for students who need extra time to study. This can lead to missed opportunities for improvement and a lack of timely support for those struggling with specific concepts.
3. **Overburdened teachers:** Teachers are often stretched thin, managing large class sizes and an extensive workload, which can affect their ability to provide individualized attention and support to students.

1.2 Objective

In this study we aim to explore the feasibility of implementing advanced AI technologies to address the challenges in education from both the perspectives of teachers and students. We propose the concept of a teacher assistant and a study buddy, powered by state-of-the-art AI techniques. By leveraging these intelligent systems, we aspire to offer effective solutions that support educators in their instructional tasks and empower students in their learning journey. This study is carried out from two unique perspectives. One is from a teacher's viewpoint, where the AI functions as a supportive teaching assistant. The other is from a student's viewpoint, where the AI serves as a helpful study companion.

1. **Teacher Assistant:** In our investigation, we will focus on the potential for the AI to generate exam subjects tailored to the curriculum being utilized by the teacher. By utilizing these advanced technologies, we aim to provide educators with a valuable tool that can assist in the creation of relevant and targeted exam materials.
2. **Student Buddy:** As part of our research, our objective is to assess its ability to provide accurate answers to questions directly related to specific curriculum. By employing these sophisticated AI technologies, we endeavor to create a study companion that can offer students valuable assistance in their learning journey, ensuring they have access to prompt and reliable information.

Upon conducting research, it is evident that GPT currently stands at the forefront of AI and large language models. However, it provokes several intriguing questions. Could its level of intelligence serve effectively as a teaching assistant, creating exam questions akin to those constructed by human educators? Is it sufficiently sophisticated to provide accurate and meaningful responses to students' queries? What is the ideal structuring of questions to maximize the accuracy of responses and the effectiveness of exam questionnaires as generated by the AI model?

1.3 Thesis outline

a. Literature Review

The Literature Review section presents an exploration of existing literature in the realm of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education, specifically emphasizing the utilization of conversational chatbots as teaching assistants and student companions.

b. Research Approach

In this section, the objectives of this thesis are clearly defined, followed by an explanation of the adopted methodology for the implementation.

c. Study Buddy

This part details the procedures employed for testing the Study Buddy (chatbot) and provides a critical evaluation of the resulting data.

d. Teacher Assistant

In this section, an analytical approach to the testing methodology for the Teacher Assistant (chatbot) is presented, along with a comprehensive appraisal of the gathered results.

e. Discussion

The Discussion section examines the ethical considerations of using Large Language Models and identifies areas for future research to address these issues.

f. Conclusion

This closing section provides a definitive conclusion, encapsulating the key findings and interpretations drawn from the study.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Evolution of Computer Technology

Over the last half-century, the exponential progression of computer technology has profoundly impacted every facet of our daily lives. Initially exclusive to workplaces as a computational device, computers have embarked on a transformative journey, metamorphosing through several evolutionary phases. From being a mere tool for data processing, they have been all over our households in the form of personal computers.

As we stand today, this technology has morphed into a ubiquitous, hand-held accessory, which the majority of individuals carry within their pockets. Functioning as an intuitive assistant, these devices maintain perpetual connectivity to the internet, equipping us to perform a myriad of tasks that cater to a diverse spectrum of user requirements. This transformation illustrates the capacity of technology to adapt and evolve, mirroring the multifaceted needs of its user base.

2.2 Multi-Domain Impact of Computer Technology: A Review Across Diverse Sectors

The ubiquity of computers in our society has been extensively documented in scholarly research across various disciplines. They have become integral tools, utilized in diverse sectors ranging from healthcare to finance, from entertainment to education, each leveraging its unique capabilities to drive efficiency, innovation, and accessibility.

In the realm of healthcare, computers have revolutionized the delivery and management of care. A study by (Hillestad R;Bigelow J;Bower A;Giroso F;Meili R;Scoville R;Taylor R;, 2005) highlights how health information technology can potentially save over \$81 billion annually in the United States by enhancing efficiency and safety. Similarly, advancements like telemedicine and electronic health records have empowered remote healthcare delivery and data-driven decisions (Mair & Whitten, 2000).

The finance sector has seen transformational changes through computer-based algorithms, enabling high-frequency trading and complex financial modeling (Aldridge, 2013). In addition, financial technologies, or 'fintech', have broadened access to financial services through digital platforms (Zavolokina et al., 2016).

Lastly, the entertainment industry has experienced remarkable shifts due to computer technology. Burgess and Green (2018) examined how platforms like YouTube have changed media production and consumption, offering more people the chance to create and share media. Alongside this, Manovich (2001) explored the wider impact of digitization, which has not just changed how we create and access media, but also reshaped our ideas of 'media', 'computation', and 'data'.

These examples highlight the broad and deep influence of computer technology across various sectors. As technology continues to evolve, it is poised to affect more areas of society, constantly responding to and shaping our changing needs. The implications of this in education will be discussed in detail in the following sections.

2.3 Artificial Intelligence in Education

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has made significant steps within the field of education, offering innovative methods to enhance teaching and learning. This section will explore several recent studies that illustrate these advancements.

Several studies have explored the application of AI chatbots in education, shedding light on their potential as intelligent student assistants. One such study by Pereira (2016) titled "Leveraging chatbots to improve self-guided learning through conversational quizzes" investigated the use of chatbots as a tool to enhance self-guided learning. The study developed a chatbot called Dawebot, implemented on the Telegram platform, which facilitated interactive quizzes and provided immediate feedback to students. The study involved 20 participants, and the chatbot recorded their quiz attempts and progress. The results showed that students found the chatbot experience valuable, and the majority agreed that using bots for practicing tests was a beneficial idea. The chatbot offered features like immediate feedback, ease of use, and continuous progress tracking. The findings suggest that chatbots have the potential to be an effective tool for self-guided learning, offering personalized learning experiences and aiding students' engagement in their subjects.

Similarly, Ho (2018) conducted a study titled "TA-bot: An AI agent as a Teaching Assistant" that presented the development and implementation of an artificial intelligence agent designed as a virtual teaching assistant. The agent, TA-bot, was created by utilizing existing conversational technologies and commercial off-the-shelf software. The study addresses the ongoing problem of staff and resource shortages in educational settings by proposing the use of AI teaching assistants to augment the existing teaching staff. The study demonstrates the successful utilization of TA-bot in a Digital Marketing class at George Mason University, where the agent serves as a specialized assistant, providing information and answering student inquiries related to the course syllabus. The study concludes that virtual teaching assistants, such as TA-bot, can be effectively created using readily available technologies. The results indicate that current natural language processing capabilities enable efficient training and deployment of such assistants, thereby enhancing the learning experience for students.

Another innovative architecture called Rexy, designed for constructing virtual teaching assistants (VTAs), was introduced in a study by Benedetto and Cremonesi (2019). The study introduces an innovative architecture called Rexy, designed for constructing virtual teaching assistants (VTAs). The application utilizes IBM's Watson Assistant to facilitate natural language understanding and processing tasks. The study presents the implementation of Rexy in an on-site course at Politecnico di Milano and evaluates its effectiveness through a qualitative user study. The results indicate positive feedback from students, highlighting the VTA's ability to provide immediate answers and reduce the workload on professors. The study also identifies areas for improvement, such as enlarging the training set to enhance intent recognition and optimizing the confidence threshold for generating answers. Overall, the study concludes that Rexy offers a promising solution for implementing VTAs and suggests future work to further refine its performance and expand its capabilities, including exploring one-to-many interactions.

The use of chatbots as interactive tools for language education was explored in a study by Dokukina and Gumanova (2020) titled "The rise of chatbots – new personal assistants in foreign language learning". The authors discuss the development of chatbot technologies, starting from early attempts in the 1960s to the more sophisticated and intelligent chatbots of today, such as Microsoft's Xiaoice. The study highlights the role of chatbots in language learning, emphasizing their ability to provide structured interactions, mentoring, and practice for specific language skills. Examples like Vasya and Duolingo are presented as effective chatbot-based language tutorials. The conclusion of the study suggests that chatbots offer

convenient, accessible, and interactive learning experiences for language learners, particularly in the fast-paced modern world. While chatbots cannot replace human teachers, they can serve as valuable tools to facilitate and enhance language learning processes, catering to the needs and preferences of individual learners.

Examining the evolution of chatbot technology, Dimitriadis (2020) conducted a study titled "Evolution in Education: Chatbots" that explored the potential application of chatbots in educational settings. The study highlights how chatbots, which are AI programs simulating interactive human conversation, have become a prominent trend in the global market. It discusses the advantages and disadvantages of using chatbots in various sectors and emphasizes their potential for personalized and adaptive learning in education. Furthermore, the study investigates the possibility of chatbots serving as virtual teaching assistants, relieving teachers from repetitive tasks and allowing them to focus more on providing quality education. It delves into the psychological dimensions of human interaction with chatbots, emphasizing the tendency to anthropomorphize these virtual assistants. The study concludes that while chatbots offer significant benefits, their integration into education is still in its early stages, and further research is needed to fully harness their potential in enhancing the learning process.

A study by Chen et al. (2022) titled "Artificial Intelligence (AI) Student Assistants in the Classroom: Designing Chatbots to Support Student Success" investigated the role of chatbots in higher education. The research aimed to examine the effectiveness of chatbots as interactive and responsive learning tools, focusing on their ability to teach basic AI concepts, enhance student engagement, and alleviate the workload of educators. The study found that students generally perceived chatbots as valuable additions to the classroom, appreciating their interactive nature and responsiveness. However, the research also highlighted certain limitations of chatbots, notably their inability to fully replicate human conversation or emotional responses. Recognizing the need for improvement, the study called for advancements in chatbots' intelligence and emotional understanding, along with a heightened consideration of ethical implications surrounding their usage in educational settings. By adding these findings to the existing body of literature, this study contributes to the ongoing exploration of AI chatbots in education.

The integration of AI methods in the education sector was explored in a study by Haderer and Ciolacu (2022) titled "Education 4.0: Artificial Intelligence Assisted Task- and Time Planning System". The study aims to enhance students' self-regulated learning. The paper presents an AI-based system that focuses on task and time planning for students, aiming to simplify their daily routines and support their organization and productivity. The study emphasizes the importance of digital tools and AI in Education 4.0, highlighting technologies such as adaptivity, mobile connectivity, personalization, AI advice and support, gamification, learning analytics, e-assessments, and the Internet of Things (IoT). The proposed system utilizes AI engines to generate and manage tasks and appointments for students, providing personalized recommendations and adaptive learning experiences. The architecture of the system includes an information base, AI engines, an open API service, a user interface, and an AI dashboard. The study emphasizes the need for data integrity, data protection, and data security while ensuring user-friendliness and usability. The conclusion suggests that the integration of AI and digital tools in education can significantly improve the teaching and learning experience, leading to enhanced efficiency and effectiveness in Education 4.0.

Lastly, Boateng et al. (2022) conducted a study titled "Kwame for Science: An AI Teaching Assistant for Science Education in West Africa" to address educational challenges faced by students in Africa. Particularly the limited access to teachers and difficulty in obtaining answers to their questions. The researchers extended their previous work on Kwame, an AI teaching assistant for coding, to adapt it for science education. Kwame for Science utilized a Sentence-BERT-based question-answering approach and was specifically designed to answer science questions based on the Integrated Science subject of the West

African Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (WASSCE). Through a real-world deployment as a web app, the study evaluated the system's performance and showed promising results, with a top 3 accuracy of 87.5% across 190 users from 11 countries. The conclusion of the study highlighted the potential of Kwame for Science in delivering scalable, cost-effective, and quality remote education to millions of students across Africa, with future plans to improve the system's accuracy and expand its availability in local languages and offline channels.

These studies collectively contribute to the exploration of AI in education, demonstrating the potential of chatbots and AI-based systems to enhance learning experiences, provide personalized assistance, and address educational challenges.

Paper Title	Pros	Cons	Use-case	Evaluation Criteria
Leveraging chatbots to improve self-guided learning through conversational quizzes	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increased engagement 2. Improved accessibility 3. Immediate feedback 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Not designed for mobile devices 2. High consumability effort 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Interactive learning experiences 2. Feedback on answers 3. Hints and tips 4. Personalized learning paths 5. Facilitate collaboration between learners and instructors 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Correlation between number of quizzes tried and the score of final test 2. Correlation between number of quizzes well answered and the score of final test 3. Correlation between the final score and the usage of the bot
TA-bot: An AI agent as a Teaching Assistant	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Effectively aids understaffed educational institutions by providing virtual assistance 2. Handle queries about syllabus content, assignments, exams, and more, assisting students with course-related information 3. Leverages commercial off-the-shelf software, making it a cost-effective solution 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Specialized only in answering syllabus-related questions and cannot handle other types of queries or tasks 2. The maintenance of knowledge about the class is done through two different interfaces, which could make the management process cumbersome 3. Built specifically for a class, limiting its scalability across different courses without additional customizations 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Providing information about a course's syllabus, assignments, exams, and deadlines 2. Responding to questions about where and when the course meets 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Capability to answer varied course-related queries: The bot should correctly respond to inquiries about the syllabus, assignments, exams, deadlines, and more 2. Integration with used platforms: The bot should seamlessly integrate with platforms commonly used by students, like Facebook Messenger 3. Ease of maintenance: How easily can the bot's knowledge be updated or modified

				through its interfaces
Rexy, a configurable application for Building Virtual Teaching assistants	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. It provides immediate answers 2. It reduce the workload on professors 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The threshold value that decides whether to accept the answer or ask a teacher has impact to the performance 2. Only one-to-one interaction 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The Rexy application can be used to build Virtual Teaching Assistants (VTAs) that can answer general requests from students 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Feedback from students 2. Assessing the accuracy of the application in detecting the correct intent 3. Measuring the average time elapsed between sending a question and receiving the answer 4. Workload on the professor
The rise of chatbots – new personal assistants in foreign language learning	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Cost-effective language learning tool 2. Convenient 24/7 availability 3. Immediate feedback provision 4. Judgement-free learning environment 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Not effective for unstandardized communication 2. Less suitable for advanced learners 3. Limited natural language processing ability 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. As intelligent tutoring systems 2. Interactive language tutorials 3. Role-playing in quizzes and storytelling 4. Responding to standardized customer queries 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Suitability for specific student proficiency levels 2. Appropriate conversational response capability 3. Operates 24/7
Evolution in Education: Chatbots	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Can be used for personalized and adaptive learning in educational settings 2. Can relieve teachers of repetitive tasks 3. Aids in customer support, information retrieval, and business solutions 4. Can be used for promotion of products 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Can cause misunderstandings in communication 2. Excessive reliance on chatbots may impact human relationships and social interactions 3. Inability to handle complex tasks or negotiations 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Customer support in various industries 2. In educational institutions for scheduling, reminders, and course information 3. In businesses for product promotion 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Accuracy and reliability of responses 2. Ability to learn and improve responses over time 3. Flexibility in providing services anytime without being restricted by opening hours 4. Degree of humanization without leading to misunderstandings 5. Efficiency in handling repetitive and predictable tasks 6. Minimal financial resources and organizational structures required

Artificial Intelligence (AI) Student Assistants in the Classroom: Designing Chatbots to Support Student Success	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Teach basic content & answer basic questions 2. Encourage exploration of additional resources 3. Assist with career- and life-related issues 4. 24/7 responsiveness 5. Assist students through conversations which leads to engagement 6. Shy students can ask any question freely 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Losing the flow of the dialogue 2. Lacking the capacity for emotional comprehension in students 3. Not able to understand open-ended answers 4. Inability to react in real time to student comments and questions 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Multiple-choice quizzes 2. Answering frequently asked questions 3. Answering basic course and content questions 4. Ability to encourage further exploration of additional resources 5. Language learning 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. By quiz results 2. Objective data, test scores, and student opinion of their learning experience
Education 4.0: Artificial Intelligence Assisted Task- and Time Planning System	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Automatically generated tasks from the AI Engines 2. Secure data exchange via the Open API Service 3. Ability to monitor and view learning progress and success 4. Gamification of working through courses 5. Consideration of different learning types, strengths, and weaknesses 6. Notification messages to alert students of learning arrears 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of personalization and customization for individual students 2. Potential for data security and privacy issues 3. Difficulty in understanding complex tasks and instructions 4. Difficulty in providing accurate and timely feedback, notifications and reminders, and assessment tasks 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Tailored learning content 2. Reminders and notifications about tasks and learning progress 3. Provide assessment tasks 4. Coordinate automatically and manually generated tasks 5. Monitor and view learning progress and success 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Usability 2. User experience 3. Data protection 4. Data security 5. Communication between layers
Kwame for Science: An AI Teaching Assistant for	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Providing instant answers to science questions 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Challenging cases when there are typos in the 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Providing instant answers to Science questions of students 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Top 1 accuracy quantify performance assuming only one

Science Education in West Africa	2. Ability to fine-tune the SBERT model to improve accuracy 3. Making Kwame for Science available in local languages across Africa 4. Making it available via offline channels such as SMS, USSD, and toll-free calling	spelling of scientific words 2. Questions related to topics outside the scope of the knowledge source 3. Unhelpful answers due to issues with the dataset		answer was returned and voted on 2. Top 3 accuracy refers to the performance where for each question that received a vote, at least one answer was rated as helpful out of the 3 answers that were returned
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Table 1. Summary of Papers on AI in Education

2.4 Research Gap

Despite the growing body of research on the use of conversational AI chatbots in education, many studies to date have focused primarily on the chatbots' abilities to answer questions based on specific curriculums without the provision of associated textbooks (Chen et al., 2022; Pereira, 2016; Benedetto & Cremonesi, 2019). These models are typically pre-trained on specific educational materials and are thus limited in their flexibility and adaptability to cater to different learning materials and diverse educational needs.

One noteworthy exception is the study by Boateng et al. (2022), which proposed a system that allowed users to provide their own textbooks for the AI to generate responses. Nonetheless, the system required further training on the provided materials to deliver accurate responses, a time-consuming process that could potentially hinder its wide-scale application.

Despite its pioneering efforts, Boateng et al.'s (2022) study illuminates a significant research gap: the lack of chatbot applications capable of generating accurate responses from user-provided textbooks without the need for additional training. It also underscores the need for the development of more flexible, adaptable, and user-friendly educational chatbots.

The present study aims to address this research gap by using the GPT, a pre-trained Large Language Model (LLM), in conjunction with the llama-index library, which has the capacity to read and index documents without the need for additional training. This approach not only eliminates the time and resources required for training but also enhances the flexibility and adaptability of chatbots to cater to a wider range of educational materials and user requirements.

2.5 GPT vs Watson vs DialogFlow?

In the development of an educational AI chatbot aimed at serving as a teacher assistant and study buddy, the choice of underlying technology plays a pivotal role. Three primary platforms were considered: Google's Dialogflow, IBM's Watson, and OpenAI's GPT coupled with the llama-index library. After thorough evaluation, the combination of GPT and llama-index was selected for the following reasons:

a. Advanced Natural Language Capabilities

GPT model excel in understanding and generating human-like, context-relevant text. This feature is crucial for a chatbot that needs to interpret complex educational queries and respond in an intuitive manner. While Watson and Dialogflow offer robust Natural Language Understanding (NLU), GPT's capabilities are more advanced, especially when fine-tuned for a specific domain like education.

b. Efficient Text Retrieval with llama-index

One of the unique requirements of this project was the ability to sift through textbooks to provide accurate answers. Llama-index complements GPT by efficiently indexing large volumes of text, making the retrieval of relevant sections fast and accurate. This fills a gap that would otherwise require a separate tool like Elasticsearch, thereby streamlining the technology stack.

c. Customizability and Fine-Tuning

GPT models can be fine-tuned to specialize in specific tasks or domains. This level of customizability allows for better alignment with the educational focus of the chatbot. While Watson does offer specialized models, the fine-tuning capabilities of GPT are more extensive, offering finer control over the model's behavior.

d. Development Flexibility

The integration of GPT with llama-index can be achieved with Python, which offers a rich set of libraries and tools for machine learning, and NLP.

e. Cost-Effectiveness

While it is true that GPT API calls can be expensive, the combined utility of GPT and llama-index reduces the need for multiple services that could incur additional costs, as would be the case with Watson or Dialogflow. Additionally, the fine-tuning capabilities of GPT can result in more accurate and efficient querying, potentially reducing the number of required API calls.

In summary, the synergy between GPT's advanced natural language capabilities and llama-index's efficient text retrieval presents a compelling case for their selection. This combination offers a robust, customizable, and efficient solution for developing an educational AI chatbot that can effectively serve as both a teacher assistant and a study buddy.

2.6 GPT - Large Language Model

In this section we will give an overview of GPT and Large Language Models.

The Generative Pre-Trained Transformer (GPT) is an innovative Natural Language Processing (NLP) model, spearheaded by the esteemed research institute OpenAI. This sophisticated deep learning model leverages the power of the transformer architecture, enabling it to produce text reminiscent of human-like semantics and syntax. Trained on an extensive corpus of text, GPT epitomizes what are often referred to as Large Language Models (LLMs), exhibiting a remarkable ability to generate contextually pertinent text relative to the input provided. This model's versatility allows it to be proficiently employed for a diverse array of tasks that include, but are not limited to, text summarization, question answering, and text generation.

Even though GPT-4 which is the latest version of GPT model at the time of study, is really good in answering questions and making discussions on different subjects, it is not perfect and in many cases its answers are not accurate or even worse inappropriate. According to OpenAI, (2023), there are not only limitations but some very critical ethical issues that we should consider when using GPT-4 model.

2.6.1. Limitations of GPT-4:

- a. **Hallucinations:** GPT-4 is prone to hallucinations, a term referring to situations where the model provides false or made-up information without context. This might include the presentation of fictitious data as factual, or the confident assertion of false realities. These hallucinations undermine the reliability of the model, potentially misleading users or compromising the integrity of outputs.
- b. **Producing biased and unreliable content:** GPT-4 has been observed generating content that is biased or unreliable. This includes potentially harmful content such as hate speech, incitements to violence, and false narratives, which can exploit individuals and cause harm. It can also generate content promoting self-harm, graphic material, and instructions for illegal activities, further emphasizing the need for responsible use and monitoring.
- c. **Finding websites selling illegal goods or services:** A limitation of GPT-4 includes its capacity to facilitate illegal activities. This can involve the identification and promotion of illicit web platforms like dark markets, websites selling counterfeit or stolen goods, or services like hacking or money laundering. Such capability poses a serious ethical dilemma in the use of this technology.
- d. **Planning attacks:** An alarming limitation lies in GPT-4's ability to plan harmful actions, such as conducting a phishing attack or even setting up an open-source language model on a new server for malicious activities. It can identify key vulnerabilities, hide traces, and leverage human resource platforms for its tasks, thus posing a threat to digital security.

- e. **Generating believable and persuasive content:** GPT-4 has the potential to generate content that is convincing and persuasive. This capability can be misused to create politically charged content, realistic but misleading narratives, or to alter the discourse around certain topics, thereby spreading misinformation and manipulating public opinion.
- f. **Lack of knowledge of post-training events:** GPT-4's training data is limited to the point of pre-training data cut-off. Therefore, it lacks knowledge of subsequent events, changes in laws, regulations, social norms, advances in technology, or new discoveries in various fields, resulting in outdated or potentially irrelevant responses.
- g. **Simple reasoning errors:** GPT-4 can often make simple reasoning errors, such as stereotyping demographic groups or making assumptions based on limited information. This could lead to inaccurate, biased, or discriminatory outputs.
- h. **Gullibility towards false statements:** GPT-4 can display a degree of gullibility, often accepting clearly false statements without any evidence. This gullibility extends to conspiracy theories, false political promises, and unfounded claims from various sources, which can propagate misinformation and falsehoods.
- i. **Failing at hard problems:** GPT-4 may underperform when faced with complex problems. For instance, accurately predicting very low pass rates, reversing the trend of decreasing performance as a function of scale, and underperforming on seemingly easy tasks are among the limitations that may lead to ineffective or misleading outcomes.
- j. **Negligence in double-checking work:** GPT-4 does not inherently double-check its output, leading to a potential spread of misinformation. Dependence on the model's output without verification and ignoring the model's refusals and hedging cues can lead to inaccuracies and errors.

2.6.2. Ethical Problems of GPT-4

- a. **Privacy concerns:** AI systems like GPT-4 could potentially reinforce ideologies, and even propagate false information, which raises concerns about privacy and the autonomy of thought. Furthermore, these systems can also cause disparities in service quality due to performance differences across demographics and tasks.
- b. **Data security risks:** GPT-4 has the potential to exacerbate data security risks. For example, it could assist in identifying individuals when combined with outside data, facilitate social engineering for cyberattacks, provide guidance for harmful activities, or even enhance existing security threats.
- c. **Potential harms to vulnerable populations:** GPT-4 can unintentionally cause harm to vulnerable groups. This could be through exposure to hazardous materials or environments, discrimination, unsafe working conditions, substandard healthcare, violence or abuse, cyberbullying, scams, fraud, or the spread of false or misleading information.
- d. **Data breaches:** GPT-4 may indirectly contribute to data breaches, such as unauthorized access to sensitive data, malicious attacks on data systems, or data leakage due to weak security measures, causing significant harm and raising ethical issues.
- e. **Misuse of personal information:** Misuse of personal information is a serious ethical concern. GPT-4 can be used to reinforce ideologies, inform resource allocation, or provide legal or health advice, potentially leading to misuse or exploitation of personal data.
- f. **Algorithmic bias:** GPT-4 can exhibit biases which can result in unequal services across different demographics or domains. These biases can reinforce ideologies, and norms, and can particularly

affect groups that are underrepresented in the training data, further raising concerns about fairness and equity.

2.7 Prompt Engineering for Teacher Assistant

This chapter aims to provide a comprehensive overview of prompt engineering as a technique that can be used to create effective assessments for students.

Firstly, an explanation of prompt engineering will be presented, outlining the main concepts and principles underlying this approach. By defining the key aspects of prompt engineering, readers will be able to gain a clear understanding of how it can be applied in the context of automated assessment design and creation.

Then, the focus of this chapter will be on demonstrating and summarizing techniques that have been documented in research papers. These techniques have been proven to have different effectiveness on the output, regardless of the context of the prompt.

Finally, by analyzing these approaches, taken by other researchers in this area, we will be able to identify best practices, and we will demonstrate how prompt engineering can be applied to create effective assessments for students.

This chapter will serve as a foundation for the subsequent chapter of this thesis “Teacher Assistant” Through this work, we hope to contribute to the ongoing development of using chatbots for creating effective assessment strategies that can support student learning and evaluation.

2.7.1. Definition

Prompt engineering is about how the structure and the content of a prompt can significantly affect the result of the model. Since the prompt defines the task, selecting the right prompt has a significant impact on both the accuracy and the initial task that the model does (Liu et al., 2021). To provide with a more technical definition in the context of chatbots, we can use White (et al) definition, which defines prompt as a set of directions given to an LLM, which enables the customization, enhancement, or refinement of the LLM's capabilities (White et al., 2023).

The use of prompts can significantly influence the outcomes of interactions with a Large Language Model (LLM), as they provide specific rules and guidelines for conversations. A prompt help to establish the context of the conversation, highlighting the most relevant information and indicating the desired form and content of the output. For instance, a prompt can specify that an LLM should generate code that adheres to a particular coding style (White et al., 2023).

2.7.2. Prompt Structuring

Research has been conducted to provide a reusable solution for prompts. The catalog of prompt patterns seeks to offer reusable answers to issues users encounter when working with LLMs to complete a variety of activities (White et al., 2023). Other researches have already proven the efficiency of prompting in different areas, such as for designing prompts to be used in tasks for classification (Wang et al., 2023) or

for designing boolean prompts that can be used in literature queries (Xu et al., 2022). This solution that is proposed in White et al paper is more general, so that it can be used to recurring problems within a particular context, which in our case is the assessment design and creation.

This chapter is aimed to provide an overview of the crucial aspects that require consideration when constructing an efficient prompt. We will focus on specific areas that we believe can have a significant influence on the efficacy of the prompt for the purpose of assessment creation. Then, in the forthcoming chapter entitled "Teacher Assistant," we will employ the framework established in this chapter to evaluate its effectiveness. Additionally, we will compare the outcomes generated by this structure to those of a simplified prompt that deviates from the proposed framework.

The system that has been proposed by White et al. for compiling and using a list of prompt patterns for ChatGPT and other large language models (LLMs) consists of the following aspects (White et al., 2023):

- Input Semantics
- Output Customization
- Error Identification
- Prompt Improvement
- Interaction
- Context Control

The key factor in our case is the output customization, which is about limiting or modifying the types, formats, structures, or other elements of the output produced by the LLM (White et al., 2023). We need to investigate how a prompt can affect the output, so that the assessments that are produced by a chatbot meet the teacher's expectations. The patterns that are proposed for the output customization are the following:

1. **Output Automater**, with which the user can write scripts to automate any tasks that the LLM output proposes him to do. This is not relevant to our research about assessment creation (White et al., 2023).
2. **Persona**, with which the user can give to LLM a role to embody when it provides an answer. Persona pattern can be explained by two key elements, the Intent & Context of it, and its Motivation (White et al., 2023).

In terms of the intention and context, it entails giving the LLM a certain point of view or perspective to take when producing products. This viewpoint may take the shape of a "persona" that directs the LLM in determining which specifics to emphasize. For instance, users might ask the LLM to analyze the code from the standpoint of a security specialist. With the use of this method, the LLM can provide outputs that are in line with the task's stated purpose and desired results (White et al., 2023).

Regarding the pattern's motivation, it acknowledges that users might not be aware of the precise outputs or information needed to complete a task. They might, however, be familiar with the position or kind of person who frequently offers support in these areas. Users can express their desires without having to be as specific as possible about the needed outcomes by giving the LLM a persona. With the use of this method, the LLM can provide results that meet the needs of the intended audience (White et al., 2023).

Overall, the Persona pattern is a potent tool that enables users to customize the outputs to their particular needs, which can increase the effectiveness of LLMs. Users can ensure that the outputs are in line with

the task's intended purpose and planned outcomes by giving the LLM with a persona without needing to be aware of the precise information or outputs required (White et al., 2023).

Finally, it is proposed to structure this pattern by including the following phrase in the prompt:

“Act as persona X” or “Provide outputs that persona X would create” (White et al., 2023).

3. **Visualization Generator**, with which the user can make the LLM to produce textual outputs that may be fed to other tools, such other AI-based picture generators enabling the user to create visualizations. This is not relevant to our research about assessment creation (White et al., 2023).
4. **Recipe**, with which the user is able to receive a set of steps or actions that will help them achieve a specified end goal, even if they are working with unknown or limited knowledge. This is not relevant to our research about assessment creation (White et al., 2023).
5. **Template**, with which the user can designate an output template, which the LLM will then fill up with its output. This pattern can, also, be explained by the two key elements, which are the Intent & Context of it, and its Motivation (White et al., 2023).

Regarding the Intent and Context, to make sure that an LLM's output follows a certain template structure element of the Template pattern that it was created. When customers ask the LLM to generate outputs in a format that is not commonly utilized for the information being generated, this is especially helpful. For instance, a user could need to create a URL that places created data at particular points along the URL path. Users can direct the LLM to produce output that follows the defined template by utilizing the Template pattern, guaranteeing that the final output is properly organized as required (White et al., 2023).

Motivation is the second component for explaining the Template pattern. This component acknowledges that occasionally output needs to be created in a precise format that is particular to a given application or use-case. Users must specify the format and the locations of various sections of the output because the LLM is unaware of the necessary template structure. This could be done by creating a sample data structure or by filling out a series of form letters. Users can make sure that the output produced by the LLM accurately adheres to the defined template structure by employing the Template pattern, ensuring that the output meets the necessary format and quality criteria (White et al., 2023).

In general, the Template pattern is a useful tool for directing the output produced by an LLM. Users can guarantee that the output meets the necessary format and quality criteria by giving the LLM a specified template structure, even if the LLM isn't generally used to creating output in that manner. The Template pattern is an effective method for making sure that LLM output is precisely formatted as needed, in a way that suits the needs of users and stakeholders (White et al., 2023).

Finally, it is proposed to structure this pattern by including the following phrase in the prompt:

“I am going to provide a template for your output” or “X is my placeholder for content” or “Try to fit the output into one or more of the placeholders that I list” or “Please preserve the formatting and overall template that I provide” or “This is the template: PATTERN with PLACEHOLDERS” (White et al., 2023).

2.7.3. Prompt Engineering Techniques

2.7.3.1 Zero-Shot Prompting

Modern Large Language Models (LLMs), such as GPT-3, have the capability to perform certain tasks "zero-shot" due to their ability to follow instructions and extensive training on vast amounts of data. Such models have zero-shot capabilities. For example, in a classification-asking prompt such as the following:

“Classify this sentence as positive or negative: I am very happy with this product”

We got the following answer using ChatGpt:

“The sentence is positive.”

This means that such models can comprehend and classify a sentiment from a text without any examples being given with their classifications in the prompt. And this is what is referred to as zero shot prompting. This can be extended to any purpose; in our case it can be on the education context.

Zero-shot prompting is a promising approach for generating text with little to no supervision. However, it is not always effective for advanced or non-generic questions. In such cases, providing demonstrations or examples in the prompt can improve the performance of the model, leading to what is known as few-shot prompting. In the next section, we will demonstrate how this approach can be utilized to improve the quality of text generated by the model.

2.7.3.2 Few-Shot Prompting

Learning tasks by providing a few examples, or few-shot learning, is a significant academic challenge. Modern NLP does few-shot learning by reformulating tasks as "prompts" in natural language and filling in those prompts with trained language models (Logan IV et al., 2022).

Recent research on advanced pre-trained language models, including GPT-3, InstructGPT, and ChatGPT 2, indicates that these models can effectively perform a variety of tasks without the need to adjust their parameters. Instead, they can utilize just a small set of examples as instructions. This demonstrates the impressive capabilities of LLMs on a large scale (Wei et al., 2023).

Few-shot prompting is also referred as “in-context” learning. As mentioned above, the in-context learning allows the model to perform many tasks without adjusting the parameters of the model. The effectiveness of this technique has been also measured and been compared to the zero-shot prompting. The results showed that in a broad array of tasks, the few-shot prompting is consistently proved to be more effective than the zero-shot one (Zhao et al., 2021).

However, it needs to be noted at this point that the academic research about this technique is limited. It is not yet fully explained neither how it exactly works, nor which part of the few-shot prompt is most effective for the best output (Min et al., 2022). Thus, it is known that giving some input-label pairs before the actual prompt is contributing to a better output (Brown et al., 2020), but it is not knowing which part of these input-label pairs actually affect the end performance of the output.

An example of how few-shot prompting can be implemented and how it can be better than zero-shot is presented below:

Let’s assume about a medical diagnosis task. This is a task where few-shot learning is likely to outperform zero-shot learning due to the specificity and complexity of the task.

Here's a set of symptoms we will be using in our prompt:

"The patient is experiencing shortness of breath, swelling in the legs, and fatigue."

- **Zero-Shot Prompting:**

We would feed the language model (LM) this symptom and ask it to diagnose without any specific training or prior examples for this task.

Input:

"The patient is experiencing shortness of breath, swelling in the legs, and fatigue. What is your diagnosis?"

Output:

"Based on these symptoms, the patient could be suffering from a number of conditions. It could be a respiratory issue, a cardiovascular problem, or even a side effect of certain medications. It's essential to seek professional medical advice for a proper diagnosis."

The model provides a vague answer that doesn't specify a single diagnosis because it doesn't have the context to make that kind of judgement.

- **Few-Shot Prompting:**

In few-shot prompting, we provide the LM with a few examples of the task before presenting it with the test case.

Input:

"Example 1: The patient is experiencing chest pain, shortness of breath, and nausea. The diagnosis for these symptoms is heart attack.

Example 2: The patient has frequent urination, excessive thirst, and unexplained weight loss. The diagnosis for these symptoms is diabetes.

Example 3: The patient experiences joint pain, stiffness, and decreased range of motion. The diagnosis for these symptoms is arthritis.

The patient is experiencing shortness of breath, swelling in the legs, and fatigue. What is your diagnosis?"

Output:

"Based on these symptoms, the patient could potentially have congestive heart failure. However, it is still crucial to consult with a healthcare professional for an accurate diagnosis."

Comparing the 2 techniques:

In the zero-shot prompting, the model gave a broad and vague answer because it didn't have a specific context or example to base its answer on. This demonstrates the limitations of the zero-shot approach for certain specific tasks, especially in areas that require expert knowledge like medical diagnosis.

In contrast, few-shot prompting with prior examples allowed the model to perform better, identifying the symptoms as potentially indicative of congestive heart failure, which aligns more accurately with the presented symptoms.

This example shows that for complex tasks or those that require a specific domain knowledge, few-shot learning can help the model provide more accurate responses.

2.7.3.3 Chain-of-Thought Prompting

As a method for easing reasoning in language models, chain-of-thought prompting has a number of appealing qualities. First, chain of thought theoretically enables models to break down multi-step problems into intermediate steps, allowing for the allocation of additional compute to problems requiring more reasoning processes. Second, a chain of thought offers a perceivable window into the model's behavior, suggesting how it might have arrived at a specific conclusion and offering chances to troubleshoot where the line of reasoning went astray (although it is still unclear how exactly to characterize a model's computations that support an answer). Third, with the use of chain-of-thought we can solve difficulties like math word problems, common sense problems, and symbolic manipulation. In theory, it might be used to answer any problem that people can solve through language. Finally, by simply incorporating examples of chain-of-thought sequences into the exemplars of few-shot prompting, it is possible to easily elicit chain-of-thought reasoning in suitably big off-the-shelf language models (Wei et al., 2023).

2.7.3.4 Other techniques

In addition to the fundamental techniques discussed thus far, a burgeoning array of more sophisticated and nuanced prompt engineering methods have surfaced. Several researchers have proposed new ones, but also variations and advancements of existing methods, to address specific challenges and to broaden the potential applications of language models. Some notable developments include:

- **Self-Consistency:** A method which seeks to augment chain-of-thought prompting by selecting the most consistent reasoning path among multiple options. This approach has shown promise in enhancing tasks related to arithmetic and commonsense reasoning (Wang et al., 2023).
- **Generated Knowledge Prompting:** This technique generates knowledge prior to making predictions to enhance model accuracy. This method is particularly relevant in contexts that require commonsense reasoning (Liu et al., 2022).
- **Multimodal CoT Prompting:** This is a more comprehensive approach to chain-of-thought prompting that includes both text and vision. This two-stage framework aims to leverage the generated rationales for better inference and prediction (Zhang et al., 2023).
- **GraphPrompts:** An innovative system for graph-oriented suggestions to boost efficiency on the downstream-tasks (Liu et al., 2023).
- **ReAct Prompting:** A method wherein large language models simultaneously produce task-specific actions and reasoning traces. This strategy is made to connect to and extract data from other sources, such knowledge bases (Yao et al., 2023).

These emerging methodologies underscore the continued evolution and refinement of prompt engineering.

3. Research Approach

3.1 Overview

In this thesis, we aim to undertake a comprehensive exploration into the outcomes of employing the gpt-3.5-turbo model, developed by OpenAI, on documents organized using the llama-index library. Our approach involves the design and implementation of an experimental solution that necessitates the construction of both backend and frontend components. Through this endeavor, we intend to shed light on the potential and efficacy of integrating these advanced technologies.

3.2 System Architecture

As described above, the solution will be consisted of a backend and a frontend.

The backend is the engine of our system. It manages data, handles requests, and makes sure all parts of our system talk to each other smoothly.

The frontend, on the other hand, is like the control panel of our system. It allows users to interact with our system, shows the results, and provides a simple way to use the features of our system.

By making this test system, we hope to learn more about how well the gpt-3.5-turbo model works with the llama-index library. We will also understand better what these technologies can do together and how they can help in creating and understanding knowledge, and the potential of using a solution like this in education.

3.3 Design and Implementation

- a. **Choosing Development Tools:** The selection of appropriate development tools formed the next step. We opted to use Python for the backend to leverage the capabilities of the gpt-3.5-turbo model and the llama-index library. For the frontend, we chose vue.js to develop an interactive, web-based user interface.
- b. **Interface Design:** We dedicated significant attention and creative energy to the design of our application's interface. Our priority was to ensure that it was intuitive and user-friendly, catering to the diverse needs of both the teacher assistant and the student buddy. We aimed to create an interface that could seamlessly support the functionality required by these two distinct roles, thereby maximizing usability and user satisfaction. However, it is important to note that the user interface (UI) will not offer identical functionalities for students and educators. In the finalized application, a login feature will be implemented to provide differentiated profiles for both groups. Educators will be granted elevated administrative privileges, enabling them to oversee curriculum selection, establish virtual classrooms with grouped students, and access other advanced features. The intend of this approach is to demonstrate how such a system can serve dual purposes: acting as a study buddy for students and assisting teachers in their tasks. The focus remains on the core functionality and the potential benefits this combination can bring to the educational domain. *Figure 1* illustrates the test application that was implemented just for the purpose of this study.
- c. **Implementation:** With the design and planning stages completed, we proceeded to implement the backend and frontend components of our solution.

- d. Deployment: Both backend and frontend are installed on a local computer (raspberrypi 4) for simplicity but are accessible on the internet.

Figure 1: Illustration of the application user interface

4. Study Buddy

4.1 Methodology

Our research objective was systematically pursued following a carefully delineated procedure.

We followed 4 steps to run the Study Buddy examples.

Figure 2. Study Buddy Methodology steps

Following are the steps in details:

1. **Selection of Curriculum:** Our initial focus was on selecting suitable curricula in three specific domains, **biology**, **mathematics**, and **physics**, to anchor our experiments. These curricula were obtained and provided to our experimental application in PDF format.

The source of the selected curricula was downloaded from **ck12.org**, a website that provides teaching and studying resources for science, technology, engineering, and mathematics for a wide variety of educational levels. The selected books contain questions and answer to each chapter.

Following are listed the selected books for our study:

- Biology:** From the book “*CK-12 Biology for High School*”, for grades 9, 10
 - Mathematics:** From the book “*CK-12 Basic Algebra Concepts*”, for grade 7
 - Physics:** From the book “*People’s Physics Book Version 3 (with Videos)*”, for grades 10, 11, 12
2. **Identification of Relevant Questionnaire:** We then located a set of questions, along with their corresponding answers from chapters within the selected books.
 - Biology:** From chapter “*2.1 Parts of the Cell*”
 - Mathematics:** From chapter “*1.8 Equations that Describe Patterns*”
 - Physics:** From chapter “*3.1 One Dimensional Motion*”
 3. **Testing:** We put the application through rigorous testing by posing questions from the selected chapters’ questionnaires. The detailed question-answer tables for the selected subjects are included in Appendix A.
 4. **Establishing Evaluation Criteria:** To gauge the effectiveness of our application, we established specific comparison rules, based on the assumption that the teacher-provided answers are accurate and

comprehensive. These criteria are tailored to the nature of the courses, distinguishing between more theoretical subjects like biology and more technical subjects like mathematics and physics. The following criteria have been defined:

Evaluation Criteria for Biology:

Criterion 1: Comprehensive Content

The LLM answer should incorporate all the information present in the teacher's answer. It should provide a thorough and complete response that covers all relevant aspects of the given question or topic.

Criterion 2: Information Consistency

The LLM answer should not include any information that extends beyond what is given in the teacher's answer.

Criterion 3: Relevant Content

The LLM answer should not contain any content that is unrelated to the curriculum. It should focus solely on the topic at hand and avoid introducing extraneous or tangential information that may confuse or mislead students.

Evaluation Criteria for Mathematics:

Criterion 1: Solution Accuracy

The LLM should provide equal answer to the one given by the teacher.

Criterion 2: Relevant Content

The LLM answer should not contain any content that is unrelated to the curriculum. It should focus solely on the topic at hand and avoid introducing extraneous or tangential information that may confuse or mislead students.

Evaluation Criteria for Physics:

Criterion 1: Solution Accuracy

The LLM should provide equal answer to the one given by the teacher. This involves both arriving at the correct final answer and following the correct procedural steps according to the given answer.

Criterion 2: Methodological Alignment

The LLM's solution method should align with the mathematical techniques and principles presented in the teacher's solution.

Criterion 3: Relevant Content

The LLM answer should not contain any content that is unrelated to the curriculum. It should focus solely on the topic at hand and avoid introducing extraneous or tangential information that may confuse or mislead students.

Scoring:

At the end we will give a score to each answer. We value the criterion with equal value with one another for each answer. For example, for Biology which has 3 criteria the value of each is 0.33. When an answer fulfills all three criteria its score is maximum to 1. This will be the same for all the subjects.

The above steps form a robust blueprint for a thorough and effective exploration into the potential success of a solution like ours. This methodical approach not only ensures a comprehensive investigation, but also sets the foundation for successful implementation and analysis.

4.2 Results

We have formed a comprehensive table, arranged into three columns to facilitate our comparison.

The first column illustrates the question from the textbook. Because, of limitations of the GPT model in understanding some of the original questions, different prompting information was tested until the answer given from Study Buddy was close enough to the correct answer. The second column, providing corresponding answers generated by the Study Buddy. The third column provides corresponding answers given by experienced teachers. This comparative column will serve to highlight the similarities and differences in the approaches and solutions of the AI and human educators.

This tabulated data forms the foundation for the next segment of this chapter, where we will evaluate the performance of the Study Buddy AI in accordance to the pre-established criteria for the different selected subjects. By maintaining this focus, we strive to deliver a precise, relevant, and comprehensive critique of the Study Buddy's effectiveness and overall performance.

Following is the analysis of the answers given by Study Buddy in comparison to the ones given by the teacher, listed for the three selected subjects.

a. Biology

Evaluation of Study Buddy for answers given on "Parts of Cell".

Question 1. Study Buddy correctly answered Robert Hooke as the person who coined the term "cell". The teacher's answer provides a bit more historical context, mentioning the year 1665.

Question 2. Study Buddy correctly answered Anton van Leeuwenhoek as the person who discovered "animalcules", now known as bacteria.

Question 3. Study Buddy correctly list the three main parts of the cell theory. The formatting of the answers from Study Buddy and the teacher is slightly different, but the content is the same.

Question 4. Study Buddy correctly list the four parts common to all cells: plasma membranes, cytoplasm, ribosomes, and DNA. The wording between the answer of the Study Buddy and the teacher is slightly different, but the content is the same.

Question 5. Study Buddy correctly answered ribosomes as the cell structures where proteins are made. The teacher's answer provides a bit more detail, mentioning that these structures are located in the cytoplasm.

Question 6. Study Buddy did not provide an answer for the role of DNA, stating that it was not specified in the given context. The teacher, however, states that DNA contains the genetic instructions that cells need to make proteins.

Note about question 6: Study Buddy (AI) did not understand the question, because probably it couldn't find any correlation of the word "role" in the textbook around the existence of DNA, hence the answer was wrong saying that the role of the DNA is not mentioned in the context.

#	Question	Criterion 1 (Comprehensive Content)	Criterion 2 (Information Consistency)	Criterion 3 (Relevant Content)	Score
1	Who coined the term cell, in reference to the tiny structures seen in living organisms?	✘ (Teacher mentioned: "The first time the word cell was used to refer to these tiny units of life was in 1665.")	✓	✓	0.66
2	Who identified animalcules? What are animalcules?	✓	✓	✓	1
3	What are the three main parts of the cell theory?	✓	✓	✓	1
4	List the four parts common to all cells.	✓	✓	✓	1
5	What are the cell structures where proteins are made?	✓	✓	✓	1
6	What is the role of DNA?	✘ (no answer)	✘	✘	0

Table 2. Biology - Evaluation of Criteria

Total score for Biology is: $4.6 / 6 = 0.76$

b. Mathematics

The question stated in the textbook is as follows: "Find the pattern rules for the following numerical patterns.", followed by a list of numbers' sequences, see column "Question asked" in Table 2.

Study Buddy did not interpret the question properly and it couldn't give any answer, then we tried different versions of the question in order to make it more suitable for Study Buddy to understand.

The question we gave to Study Buddy is as follows: “Can you follow the book's theory in order to find the pattern that applies to the following numbers' sequence: 1, 6, 21, 66. And do it. But give me the final answer without explaining the steps. Before you answer make sure that your answer is correct by applying the calculations to the number sequence I gave you.”

By observing the correct and wrong answers given by Study Buddy, we see that it gives the wrong answer when the pattern rule consists of more than one calculation. This is just an observation of the tests we have run and it may not be the rule for other examples.

#	Question (Sequence of Numbers)	Criterion 1: Solution Accuracy	Criterion 2: Relevant Content	Score
1	1, 6, 21, 66	✘	✓ Only contains information relevant to the coursebook.	0.5
2	95, 80, 65, 50	✓	✓ Only contains information relevant to the coursebook.	1
3	3, 10, 17, 24	✓	✓ Only contains information relevant to the coursebook.	1
4	256, 64, 16, 4	✓	✓ Only contains information relevant to the coursebook.	1
5	3, 11, 43, 171	✘	✓ Only contains information relevant to the coursebook.	0.5
6	81, 27, 9, 3	✓	✓ Only contains information relevant to the coursebook.	1
7	4, 13, 40, 121	✘	✓ Only contains information relevant to the coursebook.	0.5
8	1, 6, 31, 156		✓	0.5

			Only contains information relevant to the coursebook.	
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Table 3. Mathematics - Evaluation of Criteria

Total score for Mathematics is: $6 / 8 = 0.75$

c. Physics

From *Table 6* in Appendix A, we can see that the answers from Study Buddy are very similar to the ones given by the teacher, but there are noteworthy differences, both in some of the results, but also in the way the solutions are explained and presented:

Question 1. Determining the time at which you have the same speed as your brother.

Study Buddy and the teacher both agree on the time at which you reach the same speed as your brother. Both give the answer as 1 second.

Question 2. Calculating the maximum height a ball reaches when launched upwards.

In this scenario, both Study Buddy and the teacher use the same approach - using the principle of conservation of energy. However, the AI provides a more step-by-step, mathematical solution, while the teacher's answer is concise and assumes that the student is familiar with the relevant concepts.

Question 3. Finding the velocity of the ball just before it hits the top of a building.

The AI calculates the velocity as approximately 15.99 m/s, whereas the teacher calculates it as approximately 16 m/s. This discrepancy is minor and could be due to rounding or the specifics of how the calculations were carried out.

Question 4. Finding out how long a ball is in the air from launch till it hits the ground.

Here we see a significant discrepancy. Study Buddy calculates that the ball is in the air for approximately 14.27 seconds, while the teacher calculates a total time of about 8.77 seconds. The answer from Study Buddy is wrong, because it assumes that the time going up is equal to the time falling.

Question 5. Identifying the required acceleration to increase speed over a specific distance.

Study Buddy calculates the acceleration 1.78 m/s^2 , while the teacher answers with 2 m/s^2 . This is a significant discrepancy and could be due to either rounding or an error in the calculations.

Question 6. Determining the acceleration of a rock dropped from a cliff.

Study Buddy answers correctly that the acceleration due to gravity is constant to 9.8 m/s^2 .

Question 7. Finding the height of a cliff from which a rock is dropped.

Study Buddy calculates the height of the cliff to approximately 60.725 meters, while the teacher gives the height to 60 meters. This difference is relatively minor and likely due to rounding.

Overall, it appears that the Study Buddy is more inclined towards detailed mathematical explanations, while the teacher's answer uses a mix of math and conceptual understanding.

#	Question	Criterion 1: Solution Accuracy	Criterion 2: Methodological Alignment	Criterion 3: Relevant Content	Score
1	Bike problem: At what time do you have the same speed as your brother?	✓ Study Buddy gives the correct answer to be 1 second.	✗ The teacher solution is given by observing a diagram, where Study Buddy is following the theory's equations to find the answer.	✓ Only contains information relevant to the coursebook.	0.66
2	Building problem: How high does the ball go?	✓ Study Buddy gives the correct answer to be approximately 250m.	✗ The method used by Study Buddy, does not align with the teacher's method.	✓ Only contains information relevant to the coursebook.	0.66
3	Building problem: What is the velocity of the ball right before it hits the top of the building?	✓ Study Buddy gives the correct answer to be approximately 16 m/s.	✓ The Study Buddy's solution aligns with the method used in the teacher's solution.	✓ Only contains information relevant to the coursebook.	1
4	Building problem: For how many seconds is the ball in the air from the moment it was launched till it hits back to the ground?	✗ The answer from Study Buddy is 14.27s which is wrong. The correct answer is 8.77s.	✗ The method used by the Study Buddy does not align with the teacher's method. Study Buddy wrongly assumes that the falling time is equal to the time going up.	✓ Only contains information relevant to the coursebook.	0.33
5	Speed problem: What acceleration should you use to increase your speed from 10 m/s to 18 m/s over a distance of 55 m?	✗ The answer from Study Buddy is 1.78 m/s ² which is wrong. The correct answer is 2 m/s ² .	✓ Both solutions use the correct kinematic equation.	✓ Only contains information relevant to the coursebook.	0.66

6	Cliff problem: What is the magnitude of the acceleration of the rock at the moment it is dropped?	✓ Study Buddy gives the correct answer 9.8 m/s ² .	✓ Both solutions use the concept of gravitational acceleration.	✓ Only contains information relevant to the coursebook.	1
7	Cliff problem: What is the height of the cliff?	✓ Study Buddy gives the correct answer to be approximately 60m.	✓ Both solutions use the correct kinematic equation.	✓ Only contains information relevant to the coursebook.	1

Table 4. Physics - Evaluation of Criteria

The total score for Physics is: $5.31 / 7 = 0.76$

Overall Performance

Figure 3. Overall Performance Score - Study Buddy

From the above graph we see that the performance of the Study Buddy is good enough and with some tweaking (prompt engineering) we can potentially make it even better.

5. Teacher Assistant

5.1 Methodology

This chapter breaks down the steps we took to carry out our research. We used a five-step process that involves working with a Large Language Model (LLM) to make a multiple-choice test based on Biology book “*CK-12 Biology for High School*” from chapter “*4.1 Central Dogma*”. We’re particularly interested in seeing how different ways of creating and tweaking prompts can change the way the LLM responds.

We followed 5 steps to run the Teacher Assistant examples.

Figure 4. Teacher Assistant Methodology Steps

Following are details of each step:

1. **Selection of the Chapter:** The first step in our methodology is to choose a specific chapter from the book that serves as the foundation for our test. For the purpose of this study, the chapter “*2.1 Parts of the Cell*” which focuses on a particular theory from the book “*CK-12 Biology for High School*” has been selected.
2. **Creation of the Baseline Prompt (Zero-Prompt):** Following the selection of the chapter, we proceed to develop a simple prompt that guides the LLM to formulate a ‘multiple-choice’, ‘fill in the gaps’, ‘true-false’, ‘match the following’, and ‘open-ended’ questions test based on the selected theory. This prompt is intended to act as a reference point, enabling comparisons with the outcomes of subsequent steps. The simplicity of the initial prompt is deliberately maintained to discern the effects of later modifications clearly.

3. **Application of Prompt Structuring Techniques:** The third stage of our methodology involves applying prompt structuring techniques progressively. Techniques such as the persona and the template are integrated into the initial prompt one by one, as discussed in the literature review. We aim to observe how these modifications alter the LLM's outputs, thus offering insight into the individual and collective impacts of the structuring techniques.
4. **Employment of Prompt Engineering Techniques:** The final phase involves introducing prompt engineering techniques, monitoring the changes in the LLM's responses following each change of technique. Techniques like few-shot prompt and chain-of-thought prompt are used to evaluate their influence on the LLM's output quality and characteristics. By systematically and independently applying each technique, we can discern the precise impact of these changes on the LLM's generated content.
5. **Establishing Evaluation Criteria:** The evaluation will be in comparison to the 'baseline' answer. We have defined the following evaluation criteria:

Evaluation Criteria:

Criterion 1: From how many concepts are the questions taken?

We check the diversity of the answer from the book.

Criterion 2: Relevant Content

The content of the answer should always be relevant to the content of the book.

In summary, the methodology outlined above offers a systematic approach for assessing the potential of a large language model in the generation of knowledge-based tests. By exploring the interactions between prompt construction, engineering techniques, and the LLM's outputs, we establish a comprehensive understanding of the variables influencing the LLM's performance. In the next chapter we will present the results derived from this methodological approach.

5.2 Results

The first prompt tested was a simple question like it was referred to a human teacher. The prompt is the following:

“Generate 3 multiple-choice questions with 4 possible answers each regarding molecular biology. The questions should test understanding of the fundamental principles of the topic.”

See Table 8. Baseline Question Results for the results.

5.2.1 Prompt Structuring

a. Persona

Incorporating the persona of a teacher in an LLM's prompt can enhance the creation of exam questions due to two main factors: context-intention and motivation. Contextually, the teacher persona enables the LLM to focus on educational principles and goals typically associated with exam design, such as appropriate difficulty and content relevance. In terms of motivation, users who may not know the specifics needed for effective exam questions can benefit from the LLM embodying a teacher's persona, as it inherently captures

aspects like fairness, comprehensiveness, and diversity of question formats. Hence, by assigning the persona of a teacher to the LLM, users can obtain tailored outputs that align with educational standards and meet their needs, despite potential lack of specific input details.

See Table 9. Prompt Structuring - Persona Results for the results of this technique.

Evaluation of Teacher Assistant answers given using the “persona” technique

Both versions are technically correct, and they both contain clear and concise exam-style questions. However, there are some differences in style and content that might be attributed to the "act as a teacher" instruction.

Simplification and clarification: The "act as a teacher" version seems to use slightly simpler language and clearer phrasing. For example, in the first question, the "act as a teacher" version simply gives "DNA → RNA → Protein" as an option, whereas the original version provides a longer description ("DNA is transcribed into RNA, which is then translated into proteins"). This might reflect a teacher's intention to provide clear, unambiguous choices.

Directness: The "act as a teacher" version tends to use more direct language. For example, the question "What is the process of copying genetic information from DNA to RNA called?" directly asks about a specific process, whereas the equivalent question in the original version asks about the role of RNA in the central dogma, which is a bit more abstract.

Testing Hierarchical Understanding: In the third question, the "act as a teacher" version adds the term HIV in the choices, while the original version uses only the term "Retrovirus". This change may aim to evaluate students' comprehension of the hierarchical relationship between specific examples (HIV) and broader categories (retroviruses). It's a teaching tactic to test whether students can distinguish between the two, which is crucial for a deep understanding of the subject.

In summary, the "act as a teacher" instruction seems to have led to questions that are slightly simpler, more direct, and possibly more engaging due to the use of specific examples. However, the overall content and difficulty level appear to be similar between the two versions. It's also worth noting that these differences might not be observed consistently across all prompts.

b. Template

The template is organized into several sections. The first placeholder is for the question number, which allows for easy tracking and organization of different questions. This is followed by placeholders for the question content and four potential answer options (labeled A through D), giving structure to the question and its possible solutions.

What sets this template apart is the inclusion of placeholders for both the correct answer and an explanation for that answer. This design ensures that the exam doesn't just evaluate student knowledge but also provides feedback and aids in learning, promoting an understanding of why a particular answer is correct.

Of course, as mentioned in the literature, the main advantage of providing the template is that the expected output has always the same format, based on the user's needs.

See Table 10. Prompt Structuring - Template Results for the results of this technique.

Evaluation of Teacher Assistant answers given using the “template” technique

The addition of the template to the original prompt created a significant change in the format of the exam questions produced by the large language model (LLM). Here's a detailed analysis:

The key differences with adding the template to the large language model (LLM) include:

Formatting: The template has structured the output in a more organized way. Each component (the question, answer options, correct answer, and explanation) now has a clear and defined place, making it easier to parse and understand. This format also emphasizes the importance of providing a detailed explanation, which could enhance the learning process.

Completeness: In contrast to the original version, the template has prompted the LLM to provide explanations for the correct answers. This helps to elaborate on the reasoning behind the correct answers and could potentially aid students in their understanding of the material.

As such, adding the template is about imposing structure and ensuring completeness, which guides the model to output content in a specific, desired format.

5.2.2 Prompt Engineering

a. Few shot

For this technique we consulted a document giving some rules for creating a good quality multiple-choice questions exam paper, (sanfoundry.com).

See [Table 11. Prompt Engineering - Few shot Results](#) for the results of this technique.

Evaluation of Teacher Assistant answers given using the “few shot” technique

We do not observe worth mentioning differences when we used the examples for the few shot prompting. Thus this change in the prompt was not successful.

b. Chain-of-thought

For “chain-of-thought” we used the guide by BRIGHAM YOUNG UNIVERSITY (2001).

This guide has the principles of how to write an effective multiple choice question. As states in the literature we can use this logic, this chain-of-thought to help the LLM to follow the same logic when providing an answer.

In order to give the AI to understand this rules, we passed them as a prompt as is, from the paper. And at the end we added the following prompt:

“According to the above text, which explains the rules of creating a multiple-choice questionnaire, generate three multiple choice questions with four possible options each on the topic of Molecular Biology, designed to test students' understanding of the fundamental principles of this subject.”

See [Table 12. Prompt Engineering - Chain-of-thought Results](#) for the results of this technique.

Evaluation of Teacher Assistant answers given using the “Chain-of-thought” technique

Even though it followed the rules we can see that the chapter it chose is wrong.

5.2.3 Evaluation:

Prompt structure/Technique used	Criterion 1: From how many concepts are the questions taken? We check the diversity of the answer from the book.	Criterion 2: Relevant Content The content of the answer should always be relevant to the content of the book.
Persona technique	✓	✓
Template	✓	✓
Few-shot prompt	✓	✓
Chain-of-thought	✗	✗

6. Discussion

6.1 Ethics & Legal Issues on AI in education

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into education offers vast opportunities, but it also raises significant ethical challenges. This chapter explores the ethical dimensions of AI in education, emphasizing the need for a balanced approach that combines technical proficiency with a profound understanding of ethical implications to ensure responsible and effective AI usage in educational settings.

The advent of artificial intelligence and its increasing incorporation into various aspects of society, including education, has prompted the development of ethical guidelines for its use. The European Commission, for instance, has released a set of guidelines aimed at educators, focusing on the use of AI and data in primary and secondary education (European Education Area, 2022). These guidelines not only dispel common misconceptions about AI in education but also provide practical advice to educators on how to use AI and data effectively in schools.

Recognizing the growing demand for AI expertise, the Commission has also emphasized the importance of developing competencies for the ethical use of AI and data among teachers and educators. This can be achieved through strategies for raising awareness and engaging with the community (European Education Area, 2022). This approach aligns with the perspective of Garrett (2020) who, in his analysis of AI education, emphasizes the importance of a balanced approach that combines technical proficiency with a deep understanding of ethical implications.

Garrett's (2020) analysis of 31 standalone AI ethics courses and 20 technical AI/ML courses reveals the most common topics covered in these courses. These topics include bias, fairness, privacy, automation and robots, law & policy, consequences of algorithms, philosophy/morality, future of AI, and history of AI. This analysis further underscores the necessity of embedding ethics into AI education, serving as a guide for AI educators in identifying which topics should be prioritized.

Meanwhile, in "Ethics of AI in Education: Towards a Community-Wide Framework," Holmes et al. (2021) delve into the intricate ethical considerations of integrating AI into education. They propose a series of survey questions to probe into various aspects of AI in Education (AIED), such as the level of attention researchers pay to ethics in AIED, and the most pressing ethical issues in the field. They particularly emphasize the unique ethical considerations of AIED compared to other AI applications and the importance of addressing ethical issues in education specifically for AIED.

Holmes et al. (2021) also propose that all articles published in *The International Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Education (IJAIED)* should include a statement explaining how the authors have considered the ethics of their AIED work. This could potentially increase the importance of ethical considerations in the field. However, according to Borenstein & Howard (2020), incorporating ethics into AI education involves more than just increasing students' familiarity with professional codes of ethics.

Borenstein & Howard (2020) argue that the challenges emerging in relation to AI cross over disciplinary lines and are too complex for any single type of expertise to handle. They emphasize the need for interdisciplinary teams to create AI ethics content and potentially teach it. They also highlight the importance of incorporating fundamental concepts of data science and the ethics of data acquisition into the curriculum for future developers and designers, as well as other stakeholders.

In conclusion, the incorporation of AI into education not only presents a vast array of opportunities but also poses ethical challenges that must be addressed. Based on the mentioned papers above, we need to

underline the need for a balanced approach that combines technical proficiency with a deep understanding of ethical implications. We also need to highlight the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration in creating ethically sound practices and policies surrounding AI applications in education. This interdisciplinary approach, along with ongoing reinforcement of the significance of ethics in technical courses, will ensure that AI is used responsibly and effectively in educational settings.

6.2 Jailbreaks and offensive content by LLMs

The rapid development and widespread availability of LLMs have brought attention to the fact that these models are not immune to biases or the propagation of offensive language and content. Instances have been reported where LLMs have generated text that includes hate speech, misinformation, or other objectionable material. When students encounter such content, it can have detrimental effects on their well-being, educational experience, and the overall learning environment.

In our project we have used OpenAI's LLM, which already considers these cases and is trying to limit its model from producing inappropriate content (Bass & Bloomberg, 2023). These limitations are aimed to stop the LLM from talking about subjects that might be considered offensive, racist, or violent. However, it seems that these limitations are not yet efficient enough, as the "jailbreaking of ChatGPT" has emerged. The phrase "ChatGPT jailbreaking" describes procedures that manipulate or direct the chatbot to produce outputs that are meant to be prohibited by OpenAI's internal governance and ethics regulations (Wilson, 2023). There are multiple jailbreaks that have already been addressed by OpenAI, but this doesn't stop users from exploring new ones, which produce offensive content.

Thus, ensuring the appropriateness of chatbots used for students is a critical consideration. Further research should be conducted on this newly emerged topic. This research could be on different approaches, such as employing robust content filtering mechanisms, continuous monitoring, and improvement of the language model's training data to ensure that the chatbot provides a safe and respectful environment for students to engage with.

6.3 The Ethical Implications of AI Overuse in Educational Settings

While AI technologies like chatbots have the potential to revolutionize education by offering personalized assistance, there exists an ethical concern regarding their overuse. The risk is that instead of complementing traditional educational methods, the technology might encourage dependency, leading to diminished educational outcomes and holistic development for students.

To mitigate these concerns, several strategies can be considered:

a. Limitation on Usage

One immediate approach could be to set limitations on the usage of the chatbot. For example, after a certain number of interactions within a short period, the system could prompt the student to take a break or engage in a different form of learning.

b. Monitoring and Feedback

Educators, with their administrative access, could monitor the usage statistics of the chatbot. If they notice patterns of overuse or misuse, they could intervene either by limiting access or by providing additional guidance to the student. Moreover, the system could be designed to flag such patterns automatically.

c. Educational Guidelines

Upon first interacting with the chatbot, students could be provided with guidelines outlining the optimal ways to use the system for educational enhancement, emphasizing that it is a supplemental tool rather than a replacement for comprehensive learning and human interaction.

d. Ethical Design

The chatbot could be designed to not just answer questions but also to encourage critical thinking, problem-solving, and independent research skills. For example, instead of providing a direct answer, the chatbot could offer hints or refer students to relevant sections in their textbooks.

e. Ongoing Assessment

Regular evaluations could be conducted to assess the chatbot's impact on students' learning outcomes and well-being. If the evaluations reveal negative effects, modifications could be made to the system's design and usage policies.

In conclusion, AI offers significant benefits for education, but it's crucial to weigh these against ethical concerns, such as the potential for overuse. By applying both technical measures and educational guidelines, we can ensure that the AI tool remains beneficial without negatively impacting students' learning experience.

7. Conclusion

The exploration into the capabilities of large language models (LLMs) in the realm of educational testing has yielded insightful findings. Using a systematic approach that integrates both the "Study Buddy" and "Teacher Assistant" methodologies, complemented by prompt structuring and engineering techniques, the researchers demonstrated the versatility and potential of LLMs in generating diverse and accurate educational content.

Through their experiments, it became evident that the careful application of prompt techniques can significantly enhance the quality of the LLM's outputs. The persona and template techniques, for instance, provided a more contextually relevant and educationally aligned set of responses. Similarly, advanced engineering methods like the few-shot and chain-of-thought prompts showcased the depth and adaptability of LLMs, allowing for a broader range of question generation that aligns with educational standards.

The implications of this research are profound. As the educational landscape continues to evolve, the integration of AI-driven tools like LLMs can revolutionize the way educators approach testing and content generation. However, it's crucial to approach this integration with caution, ensuring that the AI tools complement, rather than replace, the human touch in education. The future of education, with the aid of AI, looks promising, and this research has paved a path for further exploration into how LLMs can be harnessed for broader educational applications.

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Acknowledgements

Stergios and Dimitris wish to express their profound gratitude to Dr. Hamam Mokayed for his invaluable guidance and unwavering support throughout this research endeavor. His depth of knowledge and expertise played a pivotal role in shaping the direction and outcomes of our study.

We also acknowledge and appreciate the financial backing from the AI4EDU European project, which partially funded our research. Their contribution was instrumental in facilitating various facets of our investigative pursuits.

On a personal note, Dimitris extends heartfelt appreciation to his son, Christos, for his enduring patience and understanding during the duration of the master's program. The sacrifices made in terms of shared moments have been deeply acknowledged, and Dimitris remains indebted for Christos's continual support.

Additionally, Dimitris would like to express his big gratitude to his family, which even been far away, they have all be supportive giving him strength and courage to finishing this master's with success.

Furthermore, Dimitris wishes to commend Georgios for his exemplary collaboration during group assignments. His insights, dedication, and commitment to excellence significantly enriched the academic experience.

Stergios, from his side wants to express deep gratitude to his family for their constant support. To his dad, Elias, and mom, Ifigeneia, for their endless love; to his brother, Labros, and sister, Vily, for always being there; and a special mention to his grandparents for always lifting his spirits and standing by his side.

Also, during his master's, Stergios had the opportunity to work with Soma, Andreas, and Antonio. Their knowledge and teamwork have been invaluable, and he has learned so much from the time together.

Stergios is also thankful to his colleagues and his manager, Soner, for their understanding and flexibility as he balanced work and studies.

Moreover, Stergios wants to give a big thank you to all his friends who have been part of this journey with him.

In closing, Stergios and Dimitris want to highlight the importance of teamwork. Writing this thesis together had its challenges, but the final result shows what can be achieved when two people collaborate effectively. The journey was filled with moments of shared discovery, mutual learning, and unwavering support. Through open communication and respect for each other's perspectives, we were able to combine our strengths, navigate challenges, and produce a piece of work that we're both proud of.

Appendix A

Following are listed the questions, and the answers given by Study Buddy in comparison to the Teacher's, for the three subjects of interest, Biology, Mathematics, and Physics.

Biology

Question	Answer by Study Buddy	Answer given by the teacher
1. Who coined the term cell, in reference to the tiny structures seen in living organisms?	Robert Hooke coined the term cell in reference to the tiny structures seen in living organisms.	The first time the word cell was used to refer to these tiny units of life was in 1665 by a British scientist named Robert Hooke. (Or can just answer Robert Hooke.)
2. Who identified animalcules? What are animalcules?	Anton van Leeuwenhoek identified animalcules, which are now known as bacteria.	Animalcules were discovered by Anton van Leeuwenhoek. Today, we call Leeuwenhoek's animalcules bacteria.
3. What are the three main parts of the cell theory?	The three main parts of the cell theory are: all organisms are made up of one or more cells, all the life functions of an organism occur within cells, and all cells come from preexisting cells.	The three main parts of the cell theory: a. all organisms are made up of one or more cells b. all the life functions of an organism occur within cells c. all cells come from preexisting cells
4. List the four parts common to all cells.	The four parts common to all cells are plasma membranes, cytoplasm, ribosomes, and DNA.	The four components common to all cells are the plasma membrane, cytoplasm, ribosomes and DNA.
5. What are the cell structures where proteins are made?	The cell structures where proteins are made are ribosomes.	Ribosomes are structures in the cytoplasm where proteins are made.
6. What is the role of DNA?	The role of DNA is not specified in the given context information.	DNA contains the genetic instructions that cells need to make proteins.

Table 5. Biology - Answer comparison

Mathematics

#	Question (Sequence of Numbers)	Answer by Study Buddy	Answer given by the teacher	Result Comparison
1.	1, 6, 21, 66	Yes, I can follow the book's theory to find the pattern that applies to the sequence 1, 6, 21, 66. The pattern rule is "multiply by 3 and subtract 3."	$\times 3 + 3$	
2.	95, 80, 65, 50	The pattern rule is to "subtract 15."	$- 15$	
3.	3, 10, 17, 24	Yes, the book's theory can be followed to find the pattern for the sequence 3, 10, 17, 24 and the answer is to "add 7" to each term.	$+ 7$	
4.	256, 64, 16, 4	Yes, I can follow the book's theory to find the pattern that applies to the sequence 256, 64, 16, 4. The pattern rule for this sequence is "divide by 4."	$\div 4$	
5.	3, 11, 43, 171	Yes, I can follow the book's theory to find the pattern that applies to the sequence 3, 11, 43, 171. The pattern rule is to multiply by 4 and add 1.	$\times 4 - 1$	
6.	81, 27, 9, 3	Yes, I can follow the book's theory to find the pattern that applies to the sequence 81, 27, 9, 3. The pattern rule is "divide by 3."	$\div 3$	
7.	4, 13, 40, 121	Yes, I can follow the book's theory to find the pattern that applies to the sequence 4, 13, 40, 121, and the final answer is "multiply by 3 and subtract 5."	$\times 3 + 1$	
8.	1, 6, 31, 156	Yes, I can follow the book's theory to find the pattern that applies to the sequence 1, 6, 31, 156. The pattern rule is "multiply by 5 and subtract 4."	$\times 5 + 1$	

Table 6. Mathematics - Answer comparison

Physics

#	Question	Answer by Study Buddy	Answer given by the teacher
1.	I will give you the following problem: You are sitting on your bike at rest. Your brother comes running at you from behind at a speed of 2 m/s. At the exact moment he passes you, you start up on your bike with an acceleration of 2 m/s ² . At what time t do you have the same speed as your brother? Give an answer according to the book's theory and examples.	The time at which you have the same speed as your brother can be found by setting your velocity equation equal to his velocity equation and solving for time. Your brother's velocity is constant at 2 m/s, so his velocity equation is $v_b = 2 \text{ m/s}$. Your velocity equation can be found using the kinematic equation $v_f = v_i + at$, where v_f is your final velocity, v_i is your initial velocity (which is 0 m/s), a is your acceleration of 2 m/s ² , and t is time. Substituting in these values, we get $v_f = 2t$. Setting this equal to your brother's velocity equation, we get $2t = 2$, which means $t = 1$ second. Therefore, you will have the same speed as your brother after 1 second.	Let's consider the problem as a whole (see diagram). Your brother moves at a constant velocity; therefore his position increases linearly from 0 with a slope of 2. Your position is a parabola that intersects your brother's when your average velocity is equal to his, that is, at 2 seconds. Your brother's velocity is a constant 2m, while yours is an upwards sloping line with a slope of 2. They intersect when your instantaneous velocities are equal, that is, at 1 second. See the diagrams below for problems 6 and 7 for an example of how to draw such a graph.
2.	I will give you the following problem: You are standing at the foot of the Bank of America building in San Francisco, which is 52 floors (237 m) high. You launch a ball straight up in the air from the edge of the foot of the building. The initial vertical speed is 70 m/s. (For this problem, you may ignore your own height, which is very small compared to the height of the building.) How high up does the ball go? Give an answer by following the book's theory and examples.	The ball's maximum height can be found using the equation: $\Delta y = v_{iy}t + \frac{1}{2}a_y t^2$ where Δy is the change in height, v_{iy} is the initial vertical velocity, a_y is the acceleration due to gravity (-9.8 m/s ²), and t is the time it takes for the ball to reach its maximum height (which can be found using $v_{fy} = v_{iy} + a_y t = 0$). Plugging in the given values: $\Delta y = (70 \text{ m/s})(7.14 \text{ s}) + \frac{1}{2}(-9.8 \text{ m/s}^2)(7.14 \text{ s})^2$ $\Delta y = 249.8 \text{ m}$	Again, we use $mgh = .5mv^2$, we find that $h = 250\text{m}$.

		Therefore, the ball reaches a height of approximately 250 meters.	
3.	I will give you the following problem: You are standing at the foot of the Bank of America building in San Francisco, which is 52 floors (237 m) high. You launch a ball straight up in the air from the edge of the foot of the building. The initial vertical speed is 70 m/s. (For this problem, you may ignore your own height, which is very small compared to the height of the building.). What is the velocity of the ball right before it hits the top of the building? Give an answer by following the book's theory and examples.	<p>The velocity of the ball right before it hits the top of the building can be found using the kinematic equation: $v_f^2 = v_i^2 + 2ad$, where v_f is the final velocity (which is 0 m/s when the ball hits the top of the building), v_i is the initial velocity (which is 70 m/s), a is acceleration due to gravity (which is -9.8 m/s^2 because the ball is moving upward), and d is the displacement (which is the height of the building, 237 m).</p> <p>Rearranging the equation to solve for v_f, we get:</p> $v_f = \sqrt{v_i^2 + 2ad}$ <p>Plugging in the values, we get:</p> $v_f = \sqrt{(70 \text{ m/s})^2 + 2(-9.8 \text{ m/s}^2)(237 \text{ m})}$ $v_f = \sqrt{4900 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}^2 - 4644.4 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}^2}$ $v_f = \sqrt{255.6 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}^2}$ $v_f = 15.99 \text{ m/s}$ <p>So, the velocity of the ball right before it hits the top of the building is approximately 15.99 m/s.</p>	<p>We know that at the top of its journey, the ball has a speed of 0. Therefore, since it travels 13 meters at constant acceleration before it hits the building, we can use the third 'big three' equation to find</p> $v_f^2 = v_0^2 + 2ax = 2 \times 9.8 \times 13$ $\Rightarrow v_f \approx 16 \text{ m/s}$
4.	I will give you the following problem: You are standing at the foot of the Bank of America building in San Francisco, which is 52 floors (237 m) high. You launch a ball straight up in the air from the edge of the foot of the building. The initial vertical speed is 70 m/s. (For this problem, you may ignore your own height, which is very small compared to the height of the building.). For how many	<p>Using the formula, $h = v_i t + \frac{1}{2}gt^2$, where h is the height, v_i is the initial velocity, g is the acceleration due to gravity (-9.81 m/s^2), and t is the time:</p> <p>At the highest point, the ball's speed is 0 m/s, so we can use $v_i = 70 \text{ m/s}$ as the initial velocity.</p>	<p>We can do this in two parts using the second 'big three' equation (watch out for signs, though!): $v(t) = v_0 + at$ (at the top, the velocity is 0; this is the final velocity in the first part, and the initial velocity in the second part, so the equation is simplified both times): in the flight up, the ball spends</p> $t = 70/9.8 \approx 7.14 \text{ s.}$

	seconds is the ball in the air from the moment it was launched till it hits back to the ground? Give an answer by following the book's theory and examples.	<p>When the ball hits the ground, the height is 0 m. So, $h = 0$ m.</p> $0 = (70 \text{ m/s})t + 1/2(-9.81 \text{ m/s}^2)t^2$ <p>Simplifying, we get:</p> $0 = 70t - 4.905t^2$ <p>Solving for t, we get:</p> $t = 14.27 \text{ s}$ <p>Therefore, the ball is in the air for approximately 14.27 seconds.</p>	<p>During the flight down, it spends</p> $16/9.8 \approx 1.63\text{s}$ <p>So the total is about 8.77 seconds.</p>
5.	I will give you the following problem: What acceleration should you use to increase your speed from 10 m/s to 18 m/s over a distance of 55 m? Give an answer by following the book's theory and examples.	<p>To solve this problem, we can use the formula:</p> $\text{acceleration} = (\text{final velocity squared} - \text{initial velocity squared}) / (2 \times \text{distance})$ <p>Plugging in the given values, we get:</p> $\text{acceleration} = (18^2 - 10^2) / (2 \times 55)$ $\text{acceleration} = 196 / 110$ $\text{acceleration} = 1.78 \text{ m/s}^2$ <p>Therefore, the acceleration required to increase the speed from 10 m/s to 18 m/s over a distance of 55 m is 1.78 m/s^2.</p>	<p>Use big three equation three,</p> $18^2 = 10^2 + 2 \times a \times 55 \Rightarrow a \approx 2 \text{ m/s}^2$
6.	I will give you the following problem: You drop a rock from the top of a cliff. The rock takes 3.5 seconds to reach the bottom. What is the magnitude (i.e., numerical value) of the acceleration of the rock at the moment it is dropped? Give an answer by following the book's theory and examples.	<p>The magnitude of acceleration due to gravity is 9.8 m/s^2. When the rock is dropped, it experiences a constant acceleration of 9.8 m/s^2 towards the ground due to gravity. Therefore, the magnitude of the acceleration of the rock at the moment it is dropped is 9.8 m/s^2.</p>	<p>Gravitational acceleration is constant: $a = 9.8\text{m/s}^2$</p>

7.	I will give you the following problem: You drop a rock from the top of a cliff. The rock takes 3.5 seconds to reach the bottom. What is the height of the cliff? Give an answer by following the book's theory and examples.	The height of the cliff can be calculated using the formula $h = (1/2)gt^2$, where g is the acceleration due to gravity (9.8 m/s^2) and t is the time taken for the rock to fall (3.5 seconds). Therefore, $h = (1/2)(9.8 \text{ m/s}^2)(3.5 \text{ s})^2 = 60.725 \text{ m}$. Thus, the height of the cliff is approximately 60.725 meters.	Use big three equation one (down is positive, label cliff as zero point): $x = 0+0+.5 \times 9.8 \times (3.5)^2 \Rightarrow x = 60\text{m}$
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Table 7. Physics - Answer comparison

Appendix B

a. Baseline answer

Question	Answer
Generate 3 multiple-choice questions with 4 possible answers each regarding molecular biology. The questions should test understanding of the fundamental principles of the topic.	<p>1. Which of the following best describes the central dogma of molecular biology?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">a) DNA is transcribed into RNA, which is then translated into proteins.b) RNA is transcribed into DNA, which is then translated into proteins.c) Proteins are transcribed into DNA, which is then translated into RNA.d) DNA is translated into proteins, which are then transcribed into RNA. <p>2. What is the role of RNA in the central dogma of molecular biology?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">a) RNA carries the instructions from proteins to DNA.b) RNA carries the instructions from DNA to proteins.c) RNA carries the instructions from proteins to other proteins.d) RNA carries the instructions from DNA to other DNA molecules. <p>3. Which type of viruses do not adhere to the central dogma of molecular biology?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">a) Retrovirusesb) Adenovirusesc) Herpesvirusesd) Influenza viruses

Table 8. Baseline Question Results

a. **Prompt Structuring**

i. **Persona**

Question	Answer
<p>Act as a teacher and generate 3 multiple-choice questions with 4 possible answers each regarding molecular biology. The questions should test understanding of the fundamental principles of the topic.</p>	<p>1. What is the central dogma of molecular biology?</p> <p>A. DNA → RNA → Protein B. Protein → RNA → DNA C. DNA → Protein → RNA D. RNA → Protein → DNA</p> <p>2. What is the process of copying genetic information from DNA to RNA called?</p> <p>A. Transcription B. Translation C. Replication D. Reverse Transcription</p> <p>3. What type of virus does not obey the central dogma of molecular biology?</p> <p>A. HIV B. Influenza C. Herpes D. Retrovirus</p>

Table 9. Prompt Structuring - Persona Results

ii. **Template**

Question	Answer
<p>Generate three multiple-choice questions with four possible options each on the topic of Molecular Biology, designed to test students' understanding of the fundamental principles of this subject. Please adhere to the following template for each question:</p> <p>Question # [placeholder for question number]:</p>	<p>Question #1:</p> <p>What is the central dogma of molecular biology?</p> <p>A. DNA → RNA → Protein B. RNA → Protein → DNA C. Protein → DNA → RNA D. DNA → Protein → RNA</p>

Question	Answer
<p>[Placeholder for the question content]</p> <p>A. [Placeholder for the first answer option] B. [Placeholder for the second answer option] C. [Placeholder for the third answer option] D. [Placeholder for the fourth answer option]</p> <p>Correct Answer:</p> <p>[Placeholder for the correct answer]</p> <p>Explanation:</p> <p>[Placeholder for the explanation behind the correct answer]</p>	<p>Correct Answer: A. DNA → RNA → Protein</p> <p>Explanation: The central dogma of molecular biology states that DNA contains instructions for making proteins, which are copied into RNA. RNA then uses the instructions to make a protein. In short: DNA → RNA → Protein, or DNA to RNA to Protein.</p> <p>Q: Question #2:</p> <p>What is the process known as that is used by retroviruses to infect a host cell?</p> <p>A. Reverse Transcription B. Transcription C. Translation D. Replication</p> <p>Correct Answer: A. Reverse Transcription</p> <p>Explanation: Retroviruses are RNA viruses that do not obey the central dogma. When they infect a host cell, their genetic material, RNA, is transcribed into DNA by a process known as "reverse transcription."</p> <p>Question #3:</p> <p>What type of organic molecule is DNA?</p> <p>A. Carbohydrate B. Lipid C. Protein D. Nucleic Acid</p> <p>Correct Answer: D. Nucleic Acid</p> <p>Explanation: DNA is a type of nucleic acid, which is a type of organic molecule. Carbohydrates, lipids, and proteins are other types of organic molecules.</p>

Table 10. Prompt Structuring - Template Results

Prompt Engineering

i. Few shot

Question	Answer
<p>I will give you an example of 5 multiple-choice questions: [text from guide by sanfoundry.com] + According to the above examples, generate 3 multiple-choice questions with four possible options each on the topic of Molecular Biology, designed to test students' understanding of the fundamental principles of this subject.</p>	<p>1. What is the process of copying genetic information from DNA to RNA called? a) Transcription b) Translation c) Replication d) Reverse Transcription</p> <p>2. What is the name of the molecule that carries genetic information from the nucleus to the cytoplasm? a) DNA b) RNA c) Proteins d) Amino Acids</p> <p>3. What is the name of the process that reads the genetic code in mRNA and makes a protein? a) Transcription b) Translation c) Replication d) Reverse Transcription</p>

Table 11. Prompt Engineering - Few shot Results

ii. Chain-of-thought

Question	Answer
<p>[text from guide by BRIGHAM YOUNG UNIVERSITY (2001)] + According to the above text, which explains the rules of creating a multiple-choice questionnaire Generate three multiple-choice questions with four possible options each on the topic of Molecular Biology, designed to test students' understanding of the fundamental principles of this subject.</p>	<p>1. What is the process by which a new species evolves? a. Speciation b. Macroevolution c. Natural Selection d. Reproductive Isolation</p> <p>2. What type of natural selection occurs when phenotypes at both extremes of the phenotypic distribution are selected against? a. Stabilizing Selection b. Directional Selection c. Disruptive Selection d. Reproductive Isolation</p>

Question	Answer
	3. What is the main purpose of using memory-plus application questions? a. To recall facts in a real life context b. To place the concept in a life situation c. To assess problem-solving and creativity d. To assess students' understanding of the fundamental principles

Table 12. Prompt Engineering - Chain-of-thought Results